

On Van, R, S topological properties of backbone DNA networks

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Abstract

The study of the intersection of graph theory and chemistry is known as chemical graph theory. In this study, we derive the Van, R, and S topological indices for networks with backbone DNA and networks with split backbone DNA. Using the direct technique, these topological descriptors are calculated.

Keywords: Van index, R index, S index, Backbone DNA network, Subdivided backbone DNA Network

MSC Classification: 05C09 , 05C07 , 05C92 , 92E10

1 Introduction

The study of nodes connected by arcs in a grid is known as graph theory. The goal of a graph was first used in fun math exercises, but it has since grown into an important area of mathematical study with applications in the social sciences, operations research, chemistry, and computer science. Graph theory's antecedents may be definitively dated to 1735, when Leonhard Euler introduced the Königsberg arc issue. The Königsberg arc obstacle was a challenging ancient puzzle that included navigating all seven arcs that span the forked river that round the island without having to cross any one of them twice. According to Euler, there is no such manner. His finding merely makes physical adjustments to arcs referenced, but it first proved the first finding in graph theory [1]. Chemical graph theory addresses all aspects of the properties of graph theory in a variety of areas of chemistry, including computational, numerical, theoretical, and biological chemistry. It also connects with computational biology and

biotechnology. With the aid of the word "chemical," it is denoted that, in contrast to graph theory, one is permitted to depend on an intuitive grasp of numerous ideas and outcomes rather than instead of explicit mathematical outcomes [2–4]. The molecule is transformed into a molecular graph by changing atoms into nodes and bonds into arcs [5, 6]. Topological indices, which are known as graph-theoretical invariants of molecular graphs, are widely acknowledged to be effective instruments for researching the chemical and physical characteristics of compounds [7, 8]. The topological indices of generalized bridge molecular networks, carbon nanotubes, and chemical graph products are covered by Zhang et al. [9–11]. The chemical and physical analysis of heat for the synthesis and entropy of ceria oxide was reported by Zhang et al. [12–14]. See [15–17] for further information.

Deoxyribonucleic acid is a chemical that provides genetic guidance for the development and operation of an organism. The structure of backbone DNA [18] is made up of two linked strands that wind around one another to resemble a coiled ladder, or double helix. The backbone of every chain is made up of alternating sugars and phosphate. Thymine, adenine, guanine, or cytosine (C) are the bases that each sugar contains. The bases cytosine and guanine, as well as adenine and thymine, form chemical bonds that bind the two chains together. The DNA backbone's base configuration can be used to encrypt biological information, such as the steps involved in producing proteins or RNA molecules. Genome refers to the whole collection of DNA that makes up our cells. It has 23 chromosomal pairs, 20,000 genes, and about 3 billion Trusted Source bases. Backbone DNA is inherited in two equal halves, one from the mother and one from the father. The sperm and egg are the sources of this fundamental DNA. Only one percent of the genome is made up of genes. The remaining 99 percent plays a role in controlling the quantity, timing, and quality of protein production in your body. As time goes on, knowledge of this "non-coding" DNA's structural DNA grows. The initial topological descriptor, the total of all distances between the locations, is the Wiener index [19, 20]. Simple networks, or graphs without several arcs and loops, are the focus of this article. The degree-based indicators known as Van, R, and S indices are discussed in this study [21–23].

Let G be a biological graph and v a vertex(atom) of G . The degree of vertex v , denoted as $deg(v)$, is the total number of edges which is incident to v . $N(v)$ is the set of all neighbouring vertices of v . The sum degree of the vertex v , denoted as S_v , is the total number of all the degrees of neighbouring vertices of v . The multiplication degree of the vertex v , denoted as M_v , is the multiplication of total number of all the degrees of neighbouring vertices of v . Van degree, R degree and S degree of the vertex v , defined as:

$$van(v) = S_v/M_v \tag{1}$$

$$r(v) = M_v + S_v \tag{2}$$

$$s(v) = |M_v - S_v| \tag{3}$$

Reverse Van degree, reverse R degree and reverse S degree of the vertex v , defined as:

$$rvan(v) = M_v/S_v \quad (4)$$

$$rr(v) = \frac{1}{M_v + S_v} \quad (5)$$

$$rs(v) = \frac{1}{|M_v - S_v| + 1} \quad (6)$$

By using Van, R and S degree concept, Van, R and S topological indices can be defined.

The first Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$Van^1(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} van(v)^2 \quad (7)$$

The second Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$Van^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (van(u) \times van(v)) \quad (8)$$

The third Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$Van^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (van(u) + van(v)) \quad (9)$$

The first reverse Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$Van^{1r}(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} rvan(v)^2 \quad (10)$$

The second reverse Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$Van^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (rvan(u) \times rvan(v)) \quad (11)$$

The third reverse Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$Van^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (rvan(u) + rvan(v)) \quad (12)$$

The first R index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$R^1(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} r(v)^2 \quad (13)$$

The second R index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$R^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (r(u) \times r(v)) \quad (14)$$

The third R index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$R^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (r(u) + r(v)) \quad (15)$$

The first reverse R index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$R^{1r}(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} rr(v)^2 \quad (16)$$

The second reverse R index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$R^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (rr(u) \times rr(v)) \quad (17)$$

The third reverse R index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$R^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (rr(u) + rr(v)) \quad (18)$$

The first S index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$S^1(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} s(v)^2 \quad (19)$$

The second S index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$S^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (s(u) \times s(v)) \quad (20)$$

The third S index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$S^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (s(u) + s(v)) \quad (21)$$

The first reverse S index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$S^{1r}(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} rs(v)^2 \quad (22)$$

The second reverse S index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$S^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (rs(u) \times rs(v)) \quad (23)$$

The third reverse S index of a simple connected graph G defined as;

$$S^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (rs(u) + rs(v)) \quad (24)$$

With the aid of all these indices, we examined the backbone DNA and split backbone DNA networks.

2 Backbone DNA network

The five-membered rings that make up backbone DNAs are seen in Fig. 1. DNA_n indicates it.

Fig. 1 An example of backbone DNA_4 network

Using the Van, R, and S indices, we compute the Backbone DNA network in this section. $7n - 2$ nodes and $8n - 3$ arcs are seen in backbone DNA networks [24]. The backbone DNA networks has the following Van, R, S vertex degree partitions which are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Vertex degree partition of backbone DNA network

Cardinality	S_v	M_v	$van(v)$	$rvan(v)$	$r(v)$	$rr(v)$	$s(v)$	$rs(v)$
$2n-4$	7	12	$7/12$	$12/7$	19	$1/19$	5	$1/6$
2	6	8	$3/4$	$4/3$	14	$1/14$	2	$1/3$
$4n-2$	5	6	$5/6$	$6/5$	11	$1/11$	1	$1/2$
$n+2$	4	4	1	1	8	$1/8$	0	1

The backbone DNA networks has the following sum and multiplication edge vertex degree partitions which are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Edge vertex sum and multiplication degree partition of backbone DNA networks

Cardinality	$(deg(u), deg(v))$	(S_u, S_v)	(M_u, M_v)
2	(2,2)	(4,4)	(4,4)
4	(2,2)	(4,5)	(4,6)
$3n-5$	(2,2)	(5,5)	(6,6)
6	(2,3)	(5,6)	(6,8)
$4n-8$	(2,3)	(5,7)	(6,12)
$n-2$	(3,3)	(7,7)	(12,12)

With the help of Table 2, the Van, R and S edge vertex degree partitions of backbone DNA networks are given in Table 3.

The following theorems give the overall Van, R, and S indices representation of the backbone DNA network:

Theorem 1. Let DNA_n be a backbone DNA network of order $7n - 2$. Then the first Van, R and S index of DNA_n are

Table 3 Van, R and S edge vertex degree partitions of backbone DNA networks

Cardinality	(van(u),van(v))	(rvan(u),rvan(v))	(r(u),r(v))	(rr(u),rr(v))	(s(u),s(v))	(rs(u),rs(v))
2	(1,1)	(1,1)	(8,8)	(1/8,1/8)	(0,0)	(1,1)
4	(1,6/5)	(1,5/6)	(8,11)	(1/8,1/11)	(0,1)	(1,1/2)
3n-5	(5/6,5/6)	(6/5,6/5)	(11,11)	(1/11,1/11)	(1,1)	(1/2,1/2)
6	(5/6,3/4)	(6/5,4/3)	(11,14)	(1/11,1/14)	(1,2)	(1/2,1/3)
4n-8	(5/6,7/12)	(6/5,12/7)	(11,19)	(1/11,1/19)	(1,5)	(1/2,1/6)
n-2	(7/12,7/12)	(12/7,12/7)	(19,19)	(1/19,1/19)	(5,5)	(1/6,1/6)

$$Van^1(DNA_n) = \frac{321}{72}n + \frac{3}{8}$$

$$R^1(DNA_n) = 1270n - 1166$$

$$S^1(DNA_n) = 54n - 98$$

Proof. Considering that $n \geq 2$, DNA_n is a backbone DNA network of order $7n - 2$.
 By definition,

$$Van^1(DNA_n) = \sum_{v \in V(DNA_n)} van(v)^2$$

$$R^1(DNA_n) = \sum_{v \in V(DNA_n)} r(v)^2$$

$$S^1(DNA_n) = \sum_{v \in V(DNA_n)} s(v)^2$$

As a result by using Table 1, the conclusion follows. □

Theorem 2. Let DNA_n be a backbone DNA network of order $7n - 2$. Then the first reverse Van, R and S index of DNA_n are

$$Van^{1r}(DNA_n) = \frac{15481}{1225}n + \frac{100102}{11025}$$

$$R^{1r}(DNA_n) = \frac{151585}{2795584}n + \frac{1896514}{136983616}$$

$$S^{1r}(DNA_n) = \frac{37}{18}n + \frac{29}{18}$$

Proof. Considering that $n \geq 2$, DNA_n is a backbone DNA network of order $7n - 2$.
 By definition,

$$Van^{1r}(DNA_n) = \sum_{v \in V(DNA_n)} rvan(v)^2$$

$$R^{1r}(DNA_n) = \sum_{v \in V(DNA_n)} rr(v)^2$$

$$S^{1r}(DNA_n) = \sum_{v \in V(DNA_n)} rs(v)^2$$

As a result by using Table 1, the conclusion follows. □

Theorem 3. *Let DNA_n be a backbone DNA network of order $7n - 2$. Then the second Van, R and S index of DNA_n are*

$$Van^2(DNA_n) = \frac{377}{144}n + \frac{207}{40}$$

$$R^2(DNA_n) = 1560n - 1529$$

$$S^2(DNA_n) = 48n - 83$$

Proof. Considering that $n \geq 2$, DNA_n is a backbone DNA network of order $7n - 2$. By definition,

$$Van^2(DNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(DNA_n)} (van(u) \times van(v))$$

$$R^2(DNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(DNA_n)} (r(u) \times r(v))$$

$$S^2(DNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(DNA_n)} (s(u) \times s(v))$$

As a result by using Table 3, the conclusion follows. □

Theorem 4. *Let DNA_n be a backbone DNA network of order $7n - 2$. Then the second reverse Van, R and S index of DNA_n are*

$$Van^{2r}(DNA_n) = \frac{132804}{8575}n + \frac{75124}{5145}$$

$$R^{2r}(DNA_n) = \frac{2040}{43681}n + \frac{617255243}{13023228064}$$

$$S^{2r}(DNA_n) = \frac{10}{9}n + \frac{53}{18}$$

Proof. Considering that $n \geq 2$, DNA_n is a backbone DNA network of order $7n - 2$. By definition,

$$Van^{2r}(DNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(DNA_n)} (rvan(u) \times rvan(v))$$

$$R^{2r}(DNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(DNA_n)} (rr(u) \times rr(v))$$

$$S^{2r}(DNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(DNA_n)} (rs(u) \times rs(v))$$

As a result by using Table 3, the conclusion follows. □

Theorem 5. *Let DNA_n be a backbone DNA network of order $7n - 2$. Then the third Van, R and S index of DNA_n are*

$$Van^3(DNA_n) = \frac{71}{6}n + \frac{3}{10}$$

$$R^3(DNA_n) = 124n - 168$$

$$S^3(DNA_n) = 40n - 56$$

Proof. Considering that $n \geq 2$, DNA_n is a backbone DNA network of order $7n - 2$. By definition,

$$Van^3(DNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(DNA_n)} (van(u) + van(v))$$

$$R^3(DNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(DNA_n)} (r(u) + r(v))$$

$$S^3(DNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(DNA_n)} (s(u) + s(v))$$

As a result by using Table 3, the conclusion follows. $\square$

Theorem 6. Let DNA_n be a backbone DNA network of order $7n - 2$. Then the third reverse Van, R and S index of DNA_n are

$$Van^{3r}(DNA_n) = \frac{612}{35}n - \frac{1642}{105}$$

$$R^{3r}(DNA_n) = \frac{156}{209}n + \frac{102}{1463}$$

$$S^{3r}(DNA_n) = 6n + 4$$

Proof. Considering that $n \geq 2$, DNA_n is a backbone DNA network of order $7n - 2$. By definition,

$$Van^{3r}(DNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(DNA_n)} (rvan(u) + rvan(v))$$

$$R^{3r}(DNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(DNA_n)} (rr(u) + rr(v))$$

$$S^{3r}(DNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(DNA_n)} (rs(u) + rs(v))$$

As a result by using Table 3, the conclusion follows. $\square$

Fig. 2 An example of backbone $SDNA_3$ network

Table 4 Vertex degree partition of subdivided backbone SDNA network

Cardinality	S_v	M_v	$van(v)$	$rvan(v)$	$r(v)$	$rr(v)$	$s(v)$	$rs(v)$
$8n+1$	4	4	1	1	8	$1/8$	0	1
$4n-2$	5	6	$5/6$	$6/5$	11	$1/11$	1	$1/2$
$2n-2$	6	8	$3/4$	$4/3$	14	$1/14$	2	$1/3$
$n-2$	6	9	$2/3$	$3/2$	15	$1/15$	3	$1/4$

Table 5 Edge vertex sum and multiplication degree partition of subdivided backbone SDNA networks

Cardinality	$(deg(u), deg(v))$	(S_u, S_v)	(M_u, M_v)
$6n+2$	(2,2)	(4,4)	(4,4)
$4n-2$	(2,2)	(4,5)	(4,6)
$4n-2$	(2,3)	(5,6)	(6,8)
$2n-4$	(2,3)	(6,6)	(9,8)

3 Subdivided backbone DNA network

We add an additional point to each arc in the split Backbone DNA network seen in Figure 2. $SDNA_n$ indicates it.

Using the Van, R, and S indices, we compute the split(subdivided) Backbone DNA network in this section. $15n - 5$ nodes and $16n - 6$ arcs are seen in backbone SDNA networks [24]. The split backbone DNA networks has the following Van, R, S vertex degree partitions which are shown in Table 4.

The subdivided backbone SDNA networks has the following sum and multiplication edge vertex degree partitions which are shown in Table 5.

With the help of Table 5, the Van, R and S edge vertex degree partitions of subdivided backbone SDNA networks are given in Table 6.

The following theorems give the overall Van, R, and S indices representation of the subdivided backbone $SDNA$ network:

Theorem 7. Let $SDNA_n$ be a subdivided backbone DNA network of order $15n - 5$. Then the first Van, R and S index of $SDNA_n$ are

$$Van^1(SDNA_n) = \frac{889}{72}n - \frac{173}{72}$$

$$R^1(SDNA_n) = 1573n - 820$$

$$S^1(SDNA_n) = 21n - 28$$

Table 6 Van, R and S edge vertex degree partitions of subdivided backbone SDNA networks

Cardinality	(van(u),van(v))	(rvan(u),rvan(v))	(r(u),r(v))	(rr(u),rr(v))	(s(u),s(v))	(rs(u),rs(v))
6n+2	(1,1)	(1,1)	(8,8)	(1/8,1/8)	(0,0)	(1,1)
4n-2	(1,5/6)	(1,6/5)	(9,11)	(1/9,1/11)	(0,1)	(1,1/2)
4n-2	(5/6,3/4)	(6/5,4/3)	(11,14)	(1/11,1/14)	(1,2)	(1/2,1/3)
2n-4	(2/3,3/4)	(3/2,4/3)	(15,14)	(1/15,1/14)	(3,2)	(1/4,1/3)

Proof. Considering that $n \geq 2$, $SDNA_n$ is a subdivided backbone SDNA network of order $15n - 5$. By definition,

$$Van^1(SDNA_n) = \sum_{v \in V(SDNA_n)} van(v)^2$$

$$R^1(SDNA_n) = \sum_{v \in V(SDNA_n)} r(v)^2$$

$$S^1(SDNA_n) = \sum_{v \in V(SDNA_n)} s(v)^2$$

As a result by using Table 4, the conclusion follows. □

Theorem 8. Let $SDNA_n$ be a subdivided backbone DNA network of order $15n - 5$. Then the first reverse Van, R and S index of $SDNA_n$ are

$$Van^{1r}(SDNA_n) = \frac{17609}{900}n + \frac{25}{12}$$

$$R^{1r}(SDNA_n) = \frac{7981}{47432}n - \frac{4215}{379456}$$

$$S^{1r}(SDNA_n) = \frac{1273}{144}n + \frac{11}{72}$$

Proof. Considering that $n \geq 2$, $SDNA_n$ is a subdivided backbone DNA network of order $15n - 5$. By definition,

$$Van^{1r}(SDNA_n) = \sum_{v \in V(SDNA_n)} rvan(v)^2$$

$$R^{1r}(SDNA_n) = \sum_{v \in V(SDNA_n)} rr(v)^2$$

$$S^{1r}(SDNA_n) = \sum_{v \in V(SDNA_n)} rs(v)^2$$

As a result by using Table 4, the conclusion follows. □

Theorem 9. Let $SDNA_n$ be a subdivided backbone DNA network of order $15n - 5$. Then the second Van, R and S index of $SDNA_n$ are

$$Van^2(SDNA_n) = \frac{77}{6}n + \frac{35}{12}$$

$$R^2(SDNA_n) = 1616n - 1218$$

$$S^2(SDNA_n) = 20n - 28$$

Proof. Considering that $n \geq 2$, $SDNA_n$ is a subdivided backbone DNA network of order $15n - 5$. By definition,

$$Van^2(SDNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(SDNA_n)} (van(u) \times van(v))$$

$$R^2(SDNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(SDNA_n)} (r(u) \times r(v))$$

$$S^2(SDNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(SDNA_n)} (s(u) \times s(v))$$

As a result by using Table 6, the conclusion follows. $\square$

Theorem 10. Let $SDNA_n$ be a subdivided backbone DNA network of order $15n - 5$. Then the second reverse Van, R and S index of $SDNA_n$ are

$$Van^{2r}(SDNA_n) = \frac{106}{5}n - \frac{58}{5}$$

$$R^{2r}(SDNA_n) = \frac{4345341}{25613280}n - \frac{537537}{25613280}$$

$$S^{2r}(SDNA_n) = \frac{53}{18}n + \frac{1}{3}$$

Proof. Considering that $n \geq 2$, $SDNA_n$ is a subdivided backbone DNA network of order $15n - 5$. By definition,

$$Van^{2r}(SDNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(SDNA_n)} (rvan(u) \times rvan(v))$$

$$R^{2r}(SDNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(SDNA_n)} (rr(u) \times rr(v))$$

$$S^{2r}(SDNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(SDNA_n)} (rs(u) \times rs(v))$$

As a result by using Table 6, the conclusion follows. $\square$

Theorem 11. Let $SDNA_n$ be a backbone DNA network of order $15n - 5$. Then the third Van, R and S index of $SDNA_n$ are

$$Van^3(sDNA_n) = \frac{57}{2}n - \frac{17}{2}$$

$$R^3(SDNA_n) = 334n - 174$$

$$S^3(SDNA_n) = 26n - 28$$

Proof. Considering that $n \geq 2$, $SDNA_n$ is a subdivided backbone DNA network of order $15n - 5$. By definition,

$$Van^3(SDNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(sDNA_n)} (van(u) + van(v))$$

$$R^3(SDNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(SDNA_n)} (r(u) + r(v))$$

$$S^3(SDNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(SDNA_n)} (s(u) + s(v))$$

As a result by using Table 6, the conclusion follows. $\square$

Theorem 12. Let $SDNA_n$ be a subdivided backbone DNA network of order $15n - 5$. Then the third reverse Van, R and S index of $SDNA_n$ are

$$Van^{3r}(SDNA_n) = \frac{527}{15}n - \frac{241}{15}$$

$$R^{3r}(SDNA_n) = \frac{67227}{20790}n - \frac{16239}{20790}$$

$$S^{3r}(SDNA_n) = \frac{45}{2}n - 3$$

Proof. Considering that $n \geq 2$, $SDNA_n$ is a subdivided backbone DNA network of order $15n - 5$. By definition,

$$Van^{3r}(SDNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(SDNA_n)} (rvan(u) + rvan(v))$$

$$R^{3r}(SDNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(SDNA_n)} (rr(u) + rr(v))$$

$$S^{3r}(SDNA_n) = \sum_{uv \in E(SDNA_n)} (rs(u) + rs(v))$$

As a result by using Table 6, the conclusion follows. $\square$

4 Conclusion

Topological indices are the graphs' numerical values in mathematics. In order to build the Backbone DNA and subdivided Backbone DNA networks, we investigated the eighteen types of Van, R, and S molecular topological indices. We then used the overall findings of these networks.

Declarations

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- **Conflict of interest** The author declares that no conflicts of interest.
- **Availability of data and materials** There is no associated data.

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